

Visiting the margins
INnovative CULTural ToUrisM in European peripheries

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the results of task T6.3 Community building and networking. The work conducted in the task aimed at raising interest in the project among representatives of communities and organisation not directly involved in the INCULTUM consortium as beneficiaries, and to establish relationships and collaborations with other initiatives working on the theme of sustainable cultural tourism.

The activities conducted by task T6.3 are strictly connected with the rest of the project's activities.

The first connection is with the work package Communication and dissemination (WP2), in consideration of the fact that the creation of the INCULTUM Network relies on the outreach work.

Secondly, the resources made available through the INCULTUM Training Portal are important to be shared in the network as valuable elements of collaboration. The online course on marketing and social branding, the book on participatory governance and models in culture and cultural tourism, and the guidelines on the use of European structural and investment funds represent, in concrete terms, what INCULTUM can offer to the Network. Complementarily, the INCULTUM Training Portal offered access to reports, seminars and publications produced the other initiatives that participate in the Network.

Furthermore, the outcomes of the work on policies and participatory model (WP4) – namely policy recommendations and think papers as well as the reflection about participatory models - represent on one hand valuable knowledge and on the other hand concrete instruments, all offered as common goods to the Network.

Data analysis and statistics (WP3) used also as sources data coming from the INCULTUM Network.

The INCULTUM network has been established as a way to leverage the project's results in the future and to trigger a multiplier effect to adapt and replicate the innovations experienced in the INCULTUM pilots in new territorial contexts. The enlargement of the use and re-use of INCULTUM outcomes is based on the capacity of the network to endorse and to feed the effort demonstrated in INCULTUM into stakeholders' consultation in new contexts, engaging there the actors committed to the sustainable development of more peripheric destinations, as it happened in the project. For this purpose, it has been particularly important to valuing the ambit of the pilot experiences in INCULTUM (WP5).

The work done in WP7 Impact, evaluation and exploitation plan is also connected with the INCULTUM Network. One example is the Stakeholders mapping activity of task T7.1 that identified a wide range of categories that form the composite target of the networking activities.

Eventually, the collaborations with the sister project funded by Horizon 2020 and with other initiatives of the EU, also in the domain of the Digital Europe Programme and its Data Space projects, have been all relevant for the construction of the INCULTUM Network and for enlarging the perspective of the action.

The target value for the indicator established at the start of the project has been reached and even overpassed, demonstrating the concrete interest that the topics addressed in INCULTUM represent for the tourism sector and for the local development.

Participatory approaches bring cultural heritage, territory management, economic activities, and people together and represent a promising path to move in a changing Europe and to find new ways of engaging with culture, nature, and heritage. Many local administrations, at municipal and regional levels, participated in the pilot activities, hosting encounters and events, debating about adoption of innovations, discussing the needs for new policies. Also, associations, foundations, action groups and individual stakeholders have been involved in the INCULTUM Network which remains as one of most important legacy of the project.

The current document is composed by this Executive Summary and 10 chapters:

- Chapter 1 Introduction
- Chapter 2 Creating interest and fostering endorsement
- Chapter 3 Establishing relationships
- Chapter 4 Encouraging factual dialogues
- Chapter 5 The 'Networking' session on the website
- Chapter 6 References to INCULTUM from the Network
- Chapter 7 INCULTUM contribution to the Network
- Chapter 8 Collaborations and participation in third party's events
- Chapter 9 Monitoring and KPIs
- Chapter 10 Conclusions

1. Introduction

This deliverable is produced by task T6.3 Community building and networking of WP6 Training and Networking. The task developed actions focused on supporting and endorsing the creation and growth of an international network of common interest among projects, organisations, experts, local stakeholders, policy makers, action groups, researchers, and representatives of the civil society. The main scope of task T6.3 lies on the circulation of the results and innovations produced in the project. This occurred at two levels: on one hand, within the networks established at local level by the individual pilots on their own territories, and on the other hand at international level in collaboration with projects and organisations that are not directly involved in the project's consortium.

The general objective of the INCULTUM Network has been to pave the way for future full-scale implementations and replications of the project's results - namely: pilot solutions, strategies, tools, and data. This was pursued by (1) creating interest and fostering endorsement towards the proposed innovations, (2) establishing relationships that can continue in the future and fostering opportunities for multiplier effects, (3) encouraging a factual dialogue among the members of the network, namely the partners, the organisations targeted by the pilots, and other actors who have shown interest during the project.

The activities of T6.3 have been articulated around the following specific objectives:

1. To inform the members of the network as part of the wide audience about the INCULTUM project. This action concerns the communication sphere. It was carried out in collaboration with WP2 Communication and dissemination. The details of the work conducted in the ambit of the project's communication are provided in the deliverable D2.3 'Report on dissemination and communication'.
2. To promote and share the knowledge gathered around the themes addressed in the project, to contribute to the scientific progresses in the domain of cultural tourism. This action concerns the dissemination sphere. As for the first objective, also this second one was carried out in collaboration with WP2 Communication and dissemination. The details of the work conducted in the ambit of the project's dissemination are provided in the deliverable D2.3 'Report on dissemination and communication'.
3. To contribute to the transfer of learning from the research phase to the implementation phase of the pilot projects in achieving their innovative solutions and to share resources gathered from the Network. This action concerns on one hand the enrichment of the Training Portal and on the other hand the piloting sphere. It was carried out in WP6, in collaboration with tasks T6.1 local training and T6.4 Training methodology and coordination, and in collaboration with WP5 Pilots. The details of the work conducted in this ambit are provided in the following Chapter 3 'Establishing relationships that can continue in the future' and Chapter 4 'Encouraging a factual dialogue'.
4. To re-use the outcomes of the stakeholders mapping, impact assessment and exploitation planning produced in WP7, as a source of information for the improvement of the networking strategies. The map discussed in the deliverables D7.1 'Stakeholder map', D7.2 'Mid-term plan for the impact and exploitation of results' and D7.3 'Updated plan for the impact, evaluation and exploitation of results' have been valuable instruments to identify and to target beneficiaries within the networking activities.

A wide range of presentations was developed in the frame of the communication and dissemination work package on one hand to raise awareness among citizens and local communities and to engage with stakeholders and experts; on the other hand to promote and demonstrate the innovations experiments, the results achieved, and in this light to advocate the concept of tourism as a tool for community identity and territorial development by policy makers, public authorities, civil society and scientists. They are all available in the Zenodo INCULTUM Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/incultum/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>).

2. Creating interest and fostering endorsement

The project is rooted on two fundamental concepts:

- experimenting with novel, unexplored pilot solutions
- and focusing on secondary, underrated territories to develop innovative strategies

To realize these objectives, the consortium engaged in on-the-ground experimentation within the pilots and conducted theoretical investigations into models of participation, creating a map of targeted stakeholders, and experimenting with data utilization.

The outcomes of the three-year endeavour are documented on the project's website and through news published on its blog hosted by the digitalmeetsculture.net online international magazine. Furthermore, an active participation in the events organized by the members of the Network as well as the organisation of local dissemination initiatives offered the opportunity to the INCULTUM partners to promote the achievements of the project.

The pilots fostered communities of practice and had a positive impact on local communities from social, cultural, environmental, and economic standpoints. By implementing cultural tourism based on living territories and communities, it was possible to demonstrate solutions that can mitigate the negative impacts of tourism by strengthening local identities and social ties. All the local activities carried out in the pilots represented a great occasion for creating interest, establishing collaborations, and fostering endorsement toward the experimented innovations.

Bottom-up local strategies for sustainable cultural tourism focused on tapping into hidden potentials in remote, peripheral, or deindustrialized areas, which are often overlooked by traditional tourism approaches. The participatory models formed the basis for co-creating innovative tools, assessing the prerequisites necessary for the future full implementation, and scaling up of the pilots, even beyond the end of the EU funding period.

A training portal was developed to provide a repository of professional and academic resources available for reuse.

Figure 1 Sharing knowledge

The work conducted both in the pilots and in the horizontal work packages, together with the training resources, have put the basis for creating interest in the project's audiences and pave the way for fostering opportunities for multiplier effects.

3. Establishing relationships

The relationships established during the project do not expire with the end of the EU funding period.

Three types of relationships have been developed:

- The local relationships established by the pilots on their respective territories
- The partners relationships established among the members of the INCULTUM consortium
- The relationships established between the INCULTUM project and the external members of the INCULTUM Network

Figure 2 INCULTUM Enlarged Network

This enlarged network represents a dynamic group of organisations that share a common interest on the creation of sustainable cultural tourism solutions for peripheral destinations.

The collaborations established during the project will continue at different levels:

- The organisations that participated in the pilots will carry on the deployment of the innovative solutions experimented, within a longer period of time, looking for wider territorial cooperation, involving new stakeholders and communities
- The partners of the INCULTUM Consortium will explore opportunities for new projects, also in the ambit of the EU funded programmes, such as Horizon Europe
- Many of the projects and members of the network that have participated in the INCULTUM Network have already expressed the interest to continue sharing information and knowledge, also in the frame of new joint projects

The number of associates in the network counts at the end of the project 37 members.

The network continues to grow, and new opportunities of collaboration are emerging on the basis of the results that the project has demonstrated.

A successful case is the invitation that INCULTUM received to participate in conferences and webinars that are taking place beyond the end of the EU funding period.

We can mention to this regard the following events:

- The presentation “Tourism, archives and culture: a digitally mediated relationship between preservation and experience” to be delivered in the frame of the Seminar on Archives and Tourism organised by the City Council of Lloret de Mar, the Diputació de Girona and the Generalitat de Catalunya, which will take place in Lloret de Mar on 23-24-25 May 2024
- The delivery and presentation of the INCULTUM promotional book at the Eureka3D workshop “Preserving Values through #MemoryTwins”, organised in collaboration with the Cyprus University of Technology and the ArtTest project in Limassol on 29 May 2024
- The participation in the Webinar “Putting People First: Methodologies for Empowering Communities in Local Development” organised by TSM - Trentino School of Management on 5/6/2024
- The presentation of the results of the INCULTUM pilot at the international congress “The Almoravid and Almohad Civilization in the Maghreb and al-Andalus”, organised in Seville in October 2024

These participations will be the occasions to continue to attract more interests in the results of INCULTUM bringing to new opportunities of collaboration and establishing new relationships.

4. Encouraging factual dialogues

The dialogue between the INCULTUM project and its network has been in the core of the networking activities carried out during action.

The blog, the participation in joint events, the invitation to join the INCULTUM events, the sharing of reports in the Training Portal, the announcements in the newsletters, all these actions have represented means to seek to engage projects, organisations, citizens, and publics, to exchange opinions and perceptions, to tell success stories, to disseminate lessons learnt and knowledge.

The debate occurred at the International Conference in Guadix has been a concrete demonstration of the effectiveness of the efforts spent by INCULTUM in this endeavour of dialogue.

Networking and collaboration among stakeholders have been targeted to generate returns and exchanges between different sectors, including but not limited to agrarian, gastronomic, arts and crafts, accommodation, cultural, as demonstrated in the results of the pilots.

The two levels of the INCULTUM action are relevant to be mentioned here since the dialogue was fostered at local level with the pilots and at international level by the WP6 efforts.

Figure 3 Two levels of dialogue

The two levels of dialogue are not distinguished by law, but it is natural that they occur within different ambits of interest. Also, it has been noted the value that the use of national language has in allowing seamless conversations in the case of the local dialogues. For this purpose, the communication and dissemination WP2 has gathered and published the presentation of the pilots in national languages, in a dedicated page on the website.

A selection of the latest cases of local dialogues is presented in the following paragraphs.

An interesting case of local dialogue is represented by the training session on “Methods for collecting and analysing tourists and visitors”. On 13 February 2024, the INCULTUM pilot coordinator Uppsala University held a training session on methods for collecting and analysing tourists and visitors.

Figure 4 GPS-logger

The session was held in Uppsala with 15 participants ranging from employees within three different

municipalities, place developers, outdoor recreation strategists, and interest organization. During four hours the participants learned about the method that was co-developed by the INCULTUM pilot and Öregrund to understand visitor engagement and behaviour. The event was an interactive learning session where the participants also had the opportunity to test the GPS loggers, what the results can look like, and how they can be analysed. The training session was intended to develop the participants' competencies to facilitate their capabilities to interact and to know what kind of information and data they need that can be delivered. Both place and destination developers (DMOs) and those who are working with GIS data participated in the interactive activities. In this case, the presentations were delivered in Swedish.

Similarly, the dialogues around the pilot in Sicily and the pilot in San Pellegrino in Alpe talk in Italian.

The former event has taken place on 29 April 2024 in Palermo.

Figure 5 Workshop on the development of the Greenway

The development of the Greenway Kaggera-Vita-Salemi is part of the pilot coordinated by GAL Elimos in the frame of the INCULTUM project. The encounter, hosted by the University of Palermo, has been the occasion to present the results of the research and to review together the status of progress of the implementation of the project, debating about opportunities and threads toward the full implementation of the initiative. The strategic objectives outlined during the event include the desire to make the food&wine connotation a key element of the Greenway, thereby conferring recognizability and competitive advantage in outdoor and experiential tourism segments. Additionally, there is an aim to actively involve local operators in enogastronomy and hospitality, making them beneficiaries and promoters of the new Greenway. On the operational front, shared criteria have been discussed for the construction of local enogastronomic offerings, encouraging the participation of new activities and aligning offerings with Greenway principles. The workshop was a wonderful opportunity to establish new connections between the pilot leader (GAL Elimos) and stakeholders of the region.

The latter event will take place in Casternuovo di Garfagnana on 20 May 2024.

Figure 6 Workshop on tourism as a tool for socio-economic development

The event hosted at the 'Vittorio Alfieri' Theatre is conceived as a dissemination space for the entire Garfagnana territory and the neighbouring Mediavalle del Serchio valley. The coordinators of the project UNIFI and the researchers involved will talk about the objectives of the INCULTUM project and the results obtained by pilot run in San Pellegrino in Alpe as an example to be replicated in more peripheral locations of the valley. The presentation will be followed by a debate to reflect on the possibilities of using cultural tourism as a tool for the socio-economic revitalisation of peripheral territories and the Garfagnana area in particular. The conference will be attended by students from the 'ISI Garfagnana' high school, provincial and regional politicians, local tourism operators, stakeholders, and teachers involved in the training activities. The event will be complemented by the theatrical performance 'Un prete, due santi, un confine e 4000 pezzi unici' (A priest, two saints, a border and 4,000 unique pieces), performed by the actress Elisabetta Salvatori. Also in this case, the event is a fantastic opportunity to enlarge the interest towards the INCULTUM solutions to new local stakeholders and public administrators.

At international level, the dialogues triggered in the INCULTUM Network have already delivered interesting impacts also beyond the actors participating in the project.

One interesting case is that of the Geopark of the South Fyn Archipelago in Denmark.

Figure 7 Promotion of The South Fyn Archipelago Geopark

Associate Professor Carsten Humlebæk of Copenhagen Business School, partner of the INCULTUM project, participated in the first ordinary meeting of the Scientific Council of Geopark The South Fyn Archipelago, of which he became a member at the inception of the Council in the summer of 2023. The Council's role is to be a partner for the Geopark's board and secretariat and provide input for new potential activities and business areas. Biologists, historians, archaeologists, and geologists sit in the Council, with responsibility for the six areas of action: Geology and nature, Teaching, Active outdoors living, Culture, and Research. A collaboration between four municipalities, Geopark The South Fyn Archipelago aims to 'create a strong common identity as a basis for local development, respecting landscapes, cultural heritage and wild nature' in the south of Fyn and the

adjacent islands and marine area. The Geopark aspires to become a UNESCO Global Geopark and received a visit by the UNESCO evaluators in June 2023 (in which the Scientific Council also participated). Carsten Humlebæk is tasked with special responsibilities in the sixth field of action, focusing on geotourism – not least due to his involvement in the EU research project INCULTUM. Several of the tools and methods that INCULTUM has resulted in can be adapted to and implemented in Geopark contexts.

This case demonstrates that the potential for development is not limited to the pilots included in the project: learning and networking are open also to other stakeholders and regions.

5. The 'Networking' section in the website

The INCULTUM Network is promoted online, through the project's blog and also in the project's website.

A section of the INCULTUM website is dedicated to the networking activities.

Figure 8 The 'Networking' landing page on the INCULTUM website

The 'Networking' section of the INCULTUM website is composed by a landing page that introduces to the scope of the activities and a submenu item that provides links and presentation of the 37 organisations that adhere to the INCULTUM Network.

The landing page points out to the 'Innovation' page of the website, where the links to the Innovation fact sheets produced by all the INCULTUM pilots are available for download.

Then a reference to the Stakeholders mapping activity carried out in WP7 is provided, listing the audiences that have been identified and targeted by the project. This list aims to attract the attention of the visitors who can recognise there the type of organisation they belong to, and consequently to feel represented in the scope of the project and encouraged to be join the network.

Because of the multiple relationships illustrated in Chapter 3 and the two levels of dialogues illustrated in Chapter 4, the 'Networking' page provides both the link to the section of the website dedicated to the pilots, and the link to the 'Collaborations' page that lists the liaisons established between the project and other organisations and initiatives.

The list provided in the 'Collaborations' page is provided in alphabetic order.

Each organisation is presented with its logo, the link to the website, and a short description.

The listed collaborations get together both the local and international factual liaisons established by the project.

They are re-grouped in the following sections, based on their specific features.

5.1. Collaborations established in the frame of the INCULTUM pilots

The following specific collaborations were established by the INCULTUM pilots.

They are in addition to the collaborations established by the pilots with several local and regional public administrations.

Pilot Desert landscapes and oasis:

- Acequias Históricas is the short name for Asociación de Comunidades de Regantes Históricas y Tradicionales de Andalucía – Association of Historical and Traditional Irrigation Communities of Andalusia. This association was established in 2015, being the first in the Andalusian territory, created to claim the value of traditional irrigation and the irrigation communities that manage them.
- The Rural Development Group Association of the Altiplano of Granada was established in 2000. The scope of action of the Association is the regions of Baza and Huéscar. The Association aims to serve as a nucleus of convergence and representation of all institutions, entities and agents, both public and private, interested in the comprehensive development of the municipalities that make up the area of action.
- Pasos is a group of professionals who dream of a free, fair and autonomous society, which has an equitable distribution of power and lives in healthy coexistence between people, with other living beings, and with the web of life.

Pilot Monti di Trapani

- Circolo Semiologico Siciliano is a non-profit cultural association that promotes the research and the dissemination of semiotic methodologies, facilitating the meeting of studies, operating in diverse sectors. The statutory activities are planned for the organization of meetings, seminars, conferences, and publications. The association owns and manages a library named to Paolo Fabbri and participates in local and international initiatives.
- GAL Valle del Belice has been founded in 2016 as a not-for-profit consortium participated by public and private organisations. It works on a territory made of 12 municipalities belonging to 2 provinces of the Western Sicily. Its strategy develops around 3 vectors: development and innovation of the local productive sectors, valuing cultural and artistic heritage, sustainable tourism.
- Parco di Segesta is one of the archaeological parks of the Sicily Region. The park manages the cultural activities connected with the visit and the valuing of the site of Segesta that is located in the province of Trapani, in the Western part of the island.
- Rete Museale e Naturale Belicina is the network of public administrations and cultural organisations committed to value the cultural, artistic and natural values of the Valley of the river Belice, in the Western Sicily, including Municipalities, Museums, Associations, Foundations and the Regional government.

Pilot Hamlet of Tuscan-Emilian Apennine: San Pellegrino in Alpe

- Fondazione Campus hosts a Study and Research Centre, focusing on the varied disciplines and problems in the field of tourism, to promote a more civilised, modern and advanced approach, in addition to its training and education vocation. A wealth of activities is held together by a simple basic design: it is the formula of the university campus which places the students at its centre, caring and nurturing them, be they young people enrolled on a degree course or professionals and managers studying at one of the schools.

Pilot Ancient paths into the future: Bibracte-Morvan

- Established in 2008, the Maison du Patrimoine Oral de Bourgogne is a regional centre that gather resources about the immaterial cultural heritage of the region. It is a space that gathers resources and

offers collaboration beyond the academic research, to experiment different forms of transmission of popular cultures.

Pilot Aaos Valley

- The P2P Lab is an interdisciplinary research collective focused on the commons. It designs and implements projects using participatory and community-based methods and practices. We forward research and knowledge through the creation of spaces for creative resistance and commons-based alternatives.

5.2. Collaborations established with international projects and organisations

Projects

- **Be.CULTOUR** stands for “Beyond CULTural TOURism: heritage innovation networks as drivers of Europeanisation towards a human-centred and circular tourism economy”. It expresses the goal to move beyond tourism through a longer-term human-centred development perspective, enhancing cultural heritage and landscape values. The overarching goal of Be.CULTOUR is to co-create and test sustainable human-centred innovations for circular cultural tourism through collaborative innovation networks/methodologies and improved investments strategies. Targeting deprived, remote, peripheral or deindustrialised areas and cultural landscapes as well as over-exploited areas, local Heritage innovation networks will co-develop a long-term heritage-led development project in the areas involved enhancing inclusive economic growth, communities’ wellbeing and resilience, nature regeneration as well as effective cooperation at cross-border, regional and local level.
- **CitizenHeritage** is an Erasmus+ project aiming at enabling citizen participation in cultural heritage, with a particular focus on citizen science and education. It will explore the degree to which Citizen Science can be an element to stimulate sustainability by promoting social ownership of cultural heritage knowledge. To do so, this project proposes the conceptualization of cultural heritage activities engagement as a cultural common in which value is created by social engagement between Higher Education Institutions, Cultural Heritage Institutions and citizens at large. The project will also examine the conditions under which Citizen Science makes both socially and economically sustainable contributions.
- **CREATOUR**. The Creatour Observatory on culture and tourism for local development focuses on 3 thematic fields: 1) Ecologies of Culture and Creativity; 2) Cultural, Creative and Regenerative Tourism; and 3) Local, Regional and Community Development, adopting a transdisciplinary perspective and critical reflection. Focusing on extra-metropolitan areas of Portugal, the Observatory is an intersectoral platform that brings together researchers and professionals from the cultural/creative and tourism sectors, in a logic of training, evaluation and co-production of knowledge with practitioners and public decision-makers. The Observatory also serves as the hub of an emerging international network – CREATOUR International.
- **ECHO II: Traditions in Transition** (September 2020 – June 2022) is a European cultural project inviting artists who work in the fields of painting, sculpture, graphic design, fashion design, craftwork and mural to create original artworks inspired by selected local traditions of North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Greece and Hungary. #ECHOII #TraditionsInTransition #EuropeForCulture
- **CulturalDeTour** project aims to use design-driven innovation and sustainability integration to boost collaboration and entrepreneurship in the cultural tourism sector, and create a strong cross-sectoral and cross-national innovation network.
- **Tourism 4.0** is an initiative in Slovenia working to unlock the innovation potential by enabling collaboration between all stakeholders of the smart tourism ecosystem to co-create enriched experiences with the help of the key enabling technologies from Industry 4.0.
- **Eureka3D** project aims to support the digital transformation of the cultural heritage sector, by offering

capacity building and training, and new services, to Cultural Heritage Institutions facing the challenge of advancing in the digitization effort, especially in 3D digitization, access, storage, sharing. The project will offer a capacity building and knowledge programme, next to services and resources developed in a piloting action based on smart technical infrastructures and tools, also registered on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

- **Geopark The South Fyn Archipelago** in Denmark covers a large area of both land and water with many local stories. It is not, as one might expect, a park with one entrance. The Geopark encompasses 2,733 km², including 1,304 km² of sea territory and has a total coastline of 551 km. The South Fyn Archipelago comprises more than 55 larger and smaller islands and is a designated Geosite of outstanding international scientific and geological value.
- **IMPACTOUR** project worked to create an innovative and easy-to-use methodology and tool to measure and assess the impact of Cultural Tourism (CT) on European economic and social development and to improve Europe's policies and practices on CT, strengthening its role as a sustainable driving force in the growth and economic development of European regions. The project has received funding from the European Commission EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.
- **IN SITU** is a four-year project that combines research and experimental actions to advance the innovation-related practices, capacities, and potential of cultural and creative industries based in non-urban areas of the EU countries.
- **I2: Identity and Innovation** project developed a participative trajectory between different actors in the sector of school education and cultural heritage. The idea is to create an integrated vision and creative solutions for a future-oriented innovation in European education, enforcing at the same time its roots and making visible its identity. At the very basis of the project's concept, there are two core challenges: enhancing the historic value of educational heritage and creating innovative surroundings and practices for schools. A programme of round tables and teaching/learning activities engaging students will enable development of best practices, exchange of knowledge and ideas, capacity building in digital skills for teachers.
- **IN LOCO** Association aims to promote local-based development with a view to improving the quality of life in its multiple dimensions, also seeing local development as a process of permanent education and civic and solidary participation. As an Associated Partner, IN LOCO collaborates with the University of Algarve in all phases of the INCULTUM project, with a special focus on the Pilot Project of the Campinas of Olhão-Faro and Loulé and on stimulating the participation of stakeholders in the governance and sustainability model to be used.
- **PAGODE** is a project co-financed by the European Union under the CEF Connecting Europe Facility Programme that contributed to generating rich user experience and high audience engagement with Europeana, the European digital library. PAGODE also supports Cultural Heritage Institutions by proposing a holistic approach in the aggregation, curation, presentation and re-use of Chinese cultural heritage preserved in Europe.
- **RURALISATION** project has identified a series of 'innovation stories' to better understand the problems associated with rural living, the importance of sustainable and inclusive farming practices, and how new thinking (dream scenarios, foresight activities) can help to transform rural communities. The ultimate aim? To open up 'rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms'. RURALISATION is working on a series of actions to support this objective with ambitious new approaches and clear options for policymakers in different contexts. These are backed by novel research methods and practical tools to create what the project calls a 'new rural frontier offering new generations stimulating opportunities for economic and social sustainability within a rural context
- **RurAllure** project is focused on the promotion of cultural heritage in rural areas along the historical pilgrimage routes. Providing pilgrims with digital tools, the project encourages them to visit lesser-known areas and discover hidden heritage sites without making major changes to the itinerary. Rural

museums and heritage sites thus add much content and value to the pilgrimage experiences, at the same time generating tourism and economic activity in local environment. The project operates along the historic itineraries in four pilot areas, each linked to a specific theme and type of heritage: Santiago de Compostela (literary heritage), Ways to Rome (thermal heritage along Via Francigena, Via Romea Germanica and Via Romea Strata), St. Olav Ways (ethnographic heritage) and Way of Mary (natural heritage).

- **RURITAGE** is a four-year-long EU-funded research project, initiated June 2018, which strives to enable rural regeneration through heritage. The project aims to sustainably enhance local heritage for regional and community development. The intention is to regenerate rural areas with the help of the Systemic Innovation Areas (SIA) framework which identifies unique heritage potential within rural communities. The recognised SIAs are Pilgrimage, Resilience, Sustainable Local Food Production, Integrated Landscape Management, Migration and Art and Festivals.
- **SmartCulTour** supports regional development in all European regions with important tangible and intangible cultural assets, particularly those located in rural peripheries and the urban fringe, through sustainable cultural tourism. SmartCulTour redefines cultural tourism through a contemporary lens and provides a comprehensive measurement framework for supply, demand and impacts. The project contributes to theory development, empirical validation of best practices within a living labs setting, and procedural development, particularly by providing European regions with a set of strategies to optimally engage with stakeholders and co-create sustainable cultural tourism experiences.
- **SPOT** project aims to develop a new approach to understanding and addressing cultural tourism and to promote the development of disadvantaged areas. Specifically, it will identify different layers of data and capitalise on existing practice. It will explore emerging forms of cultural tourism, identifying opportunities and developing strategies to allow local people to gain benefit from their precious cultural assets. SPOT will engage academics and stakeholders in the development of policy proposals and generalise lessons learnt through an Innovation Tool to assist policymakers and practitioners.
- **TEXTOUR** project co-designs pioneering and sustainable cultural tourism strategies and policies. The ultimate goal is to improve deprived areas in Europe and beyond. To do this, it sets up Cultural Tourism Labs at eight pilots located within the EU and outside it. Various societal players and stakeholders in the Cultural Tourism sector will be involved in the Cultural Tourism Labs. The selected pilots have diverse and complementary characteristics, which enables the project's experts to develop a wide range of scenarios for inland and coastal areas, rural and urban, deprived remote or peripheral areas, facing multiple social, economic and environmental challenges.
- **Tourism 4.0 for the Black Sea** project aims to demonstrate the potential of Data Analytics for tourism development in the area of Black Sea. This will enable local stakeholders from public and private sector in tourism to increase their understanding of current trends, patterns of tourist flows and impact of visitors as well as predict the tourist impact for taking strategic data driven decisions to foster more sustainable tourism in the future. For this reason, collaboration of all stakeholders of tourism ecosystem as well as exchange of data between them will be promoted to spur innovative touristic services and policies tailored to the regional challenges and opportunities.
- **UNCHARTED** project studies the emergence of values connected with culture, their configuration and the political impulse that these values could deliver to the society. It also focuses on the valuation practices of the actors involved in cultural life, especially in the areas of cultural participation, cultural production and heritage, and cultural administration. From a European perspective culture has a very strong economic impact as it generates a high volume of employment, but it is also a powerful resource for fighting the main threats that undermine the peaceful coexistence in Europe. In this light, it is worth that cultural policies consider the strategic plural values of culture.
- **WEAVE** – Widen European Access to cultural communities Via Europeana - developed a framework to link the tangible and intangible heritage of cultural communities, safeguarding the rich and invaluable cultural heritage which they represent. In particular, the project aggregated over 5,000 new high-

quality records to Europeana and carried out several capacity building activities to develop a closer connection between cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), minority cultural communities and Europeana.

Individual organisations

- **Arctur** is a Hi-Tech SME and the main private-owned supplier of HPC (High Performance Computing) services and solutions in CEE. The company has extensive experience in the deployment of complex IT systems for small and media enterprises (SME) in various sectors: from manufacturing to tourism and cultural heritage. Arctur is also the leader of the international Tourism 4.0 initiative, dedicated to transforming tourism into the driver of the UN Sustainable Development Goals by use of the key enabling technologies from Industry 4.0.
- The **Centre for Social Studies of the University of Coimbra** is a scientific institution focused on research and advanced training within the Social Sciences and the Humanities, through an inter and transdisciplinary approach. The Ministry of Science granted CES the status of Associated Laboratory in 2002, recognizing its contribution to public policies, advanced training and the dissemination and sharing of knowledge. Since its foundation, in 1978, CES has been conducting research with and for an inclusive, innovative and reflexive society by promoting creative critical approaches in the face of some of the most urging challenges of contemporary societies. CES has over 800 people, including Researchers, Post-Doctoral Researchers, Doctoral Students, Junior Researchers and Staff.
- **PHOTOCONSORTIUM** – International Consortium for Photographic Heritage is a non for profit association devoted to the promotion and enhancement of the culture of photography and photographic heritage, and is committed in the areas of digital cultural heritage, access and reuse of cultural content, citizens’ engagement and education. PHOTOCONSORTIUM participates, and promotes the participation of its members, in projects and initiatives, including but not limited to participation in the Programmes of the European Commission, and organizes photographic exhibitions, co-creation and participative events, seminars and conferences, and training courses. PHOTOCONSORTIUM is also the expert hub on photography for Europeana.eu, the Europeana digital gateway to cultural heritage, and operates as accredited aggregator for photographic collections, supporting public and private photographic archives in making their collections available in Europeana.
- **PostScriptum** is specialized in the support to digital transformation processes of Cultural Heritage Institutions, in particular by offering consultancy and deployment of software services related to Digital Heritage, including Collection Management Systems as well as web presence and new channels of communication for Museums and other organisations in the sector of culture, community engagement and tourism. PostScriptum is currently a partner of the project ECHO II: Traditions in Transitions which aims at tightening and promoting the link between artistic creation and local traditions, enabling contemporary artistic creation based on cultural elements from different European communities.
- The **Universidad de Burgos (UBU)** was created on 1994 in Burgos (Spain). It is a public university which develops its mission with a comprehensive and quality education, close to the student, focused on internationalization and which, in only 25 years, has become a reference in Spanish university research and in the transfer of knowledge towards business. The University of Burgos is located within the Campus of San Amaro, which boasts an extremely fine historic and artistic enclave: the **Hospital del Rey**. A former hospital for pilgrims of the Road to Santiago founded in 1195 by Alfonso VII is the focus of cultural tourism research at the University of Burgos.

6. References to INCULTUM from the Network

The members of the INCULTUM Network have promoted the project on their communication channels.

The following reference were published on the websites of some of them.

- Heritage Research Hub managed by the Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage:
<https://www.heritageresearch-hub.eu/project/incultum/>

Figure 9 INCULTUM page on the Heritage Research Hub

- Social and Innovative Platform on Cultural Tourism, created by the SPOT project:
<http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/incultum>

Figure 10 INCULTUM page on the SPOT Platform

- Community Platform of IMPACTOUR (registration needed):
<https://www.impactour.eu/events/measuring-impact-cultural-tourism-incultum-data-workshop>

Figure 11 INCULTUM post on the IMPACTOUR Platform

- UNCHARTED Community:

<https://uncharted-culture.eu/network-2/uncharted-community/incultum>

Figure 12 INCULTUM page on the UNCHARTED Community

- INSITU LinkedIn Community:

Figure 13 INCULTUM Conference in the LinkedIn Community of INSITU

- Eureka3D community:

Figure 14 INCULTUM Conference on the Eureka3D website

The presence of INCULTUM references on third-party websites is a direct acknowledgment of the collaborations established in the Network.

7. INCULTUM contributions to the Network

The outcomes of the research and innovation activities carried out during the project have been ‘food for thought’ for the members of the INCULTUM Network.

Particularly relevant for the Network are the policy tools developed in the frame of WP4, accessible online in the Policy Toolbox of the website, and described in deliverable D4.5 Policy Outputs.

In addition to policy matters, the following three knowledge contributions from INCULTUM are demonstrating to be relevant for the organisations involved in the Network:

- The online course on marketing and social branding produced under the scientific coordination of the UNIPI
- The book on participatory governance and models in culture and cultural tourism published by UMB
- The guidelines on the use of European structural and investment funds developed by SDU

The following sections illustrate the contents of these products.

7.1. Online course on marketing and social branding

This course has been developed by the University of Pisa.

It comprises structured videos complemented by Further Information Materials (FIMs) and self-assessment tools. All the resources are available for download from the project’s website.

Figure 15 Overview of the course on Marketing and Social Branding

The scope of the course is to address the question of how marketing and local communities can contribute to transforming peripheral areas into sustainable tourism destinations. For this scope, it offers training materials to learn about branding, communication, and participatory planning mechanisms, to allow student and professionals to operate on the territory and to obtain results. The contents are addressed from a double perspective: a theoretical framework together with a practical approach through cases, tools, examples, and interviews to professionals.

The structure of the course is based on three thematic sections:

- Section 1 is dedicated to marketing and branding principles
- Section 2 is dedicated to destination promotion and storytelling
- Section 3 is dedicated to the involvement of local stakeholders

All sections include thematic insights, such as the significance of ecomuseums as pivotal actors in the cultural tourist development of peripheral areas, the role of community managers in coordinating participation mechanisms in local development, and the rising prominence of gamification as a widely utilized mode of engagement.

This course is also available in the Zenodo INCULTUM Community (<https://zenodo.org/records/11002700>).

7.2. Participatory governance and models in culture and cultural tourism

The book is edited and published by Matej Bell University.

It offers a comprehensive exploration of culture, tourism, participation, and digitalization within the context of sustainable development, providing valuable insights and examples for professionals and researchers in the field. It is available for free download from the project's website and on the Zenodo INCULTUM Community (<https://zenodo.org/records/10950510>).

Figure 16 Book on Participatory governance and models

The book delves into concepts such as creative tourism, rural tourism, and participatory governance in culture and tourism, examining various models and approaches. It also explores the role of digitalization in sustainable cultural tourism, highlighting its significant impact on the industry. A significant portion of the book is dedicated to introducing the innovative INCULTUM Participatory Framework, which presents a fresh perspective on cultural tourism in marginal and peripheral areas. The framework is designed to promote participation and engagement within these regions.

Moreover, the book presents a diverse range of case studies and best practices that illustrate the implementation of digitalization and participatory approaches in cultural tourism. These case studies encompass various areas, including rural heritage, institutional heritage, small towns, pilgrim cultural activities, refugee integration, grassroots heritage projects, cultural centre development, and interactive exhibitions.

7.3. Guidelines on the use of European structural and investment funds

This report has been developed by Southern Denmark University.

The D6.2 is available in Zenodo INCULTUM Community (<https://zenodo.org/records/10843175>).

The document analyses the experiences of INCULTUM pilots with the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), providing insights into their application, management, and impact on cultural heritage projects.

Challenges and opportunities are analysed to highlights factors of success, focusing on administrative complexity, local engagement and innovation and sustainability. Pilots frequently encountered bureaucratic

challenges in accessing and managing ESIF, demonstrating an existing administrative complexity that risks jeopardising the success of the actions. The closest alignment with local contexts and the active involvement of community stakeholders are factors of success. Innovative approaches in project design and a focus on sustainability were key factors in the success of several pilots.

Some recommendations are then illustrated for the use of the managers of the programmes to orientate their policy and fund design. Regarding the application processes, procedures need to be simplified and supportive services are necessary for applicants to enhance the accessibility of to the Funds. For the adoption of community-centric approaches, projects should be designed as rooted in local needs and being able to involve communities in planning and implementation. A good balance between innovation and tradition is worth to be fostered in the implementation of the funding programmes, integrating modern technologies with traditional practices in cultural heritage projects.

An overview is provided on of how the INCULTUM pilots cope with the objectives indicated in the Common Provisions Regulation and with the Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) approach.

Eventually, a set of integrated guidelines are presented, aimed at enhancing the effectiveness, accessibility, and impact of ESIF, regarding five ambits of operations:

1. Streamlining and simplifying procedures
2. Adaptive and responsive funding approaches
3. Collaborative networks and community-centric approaches
4. Sustainable development and environmental considerations
5. Innovation, inclusivity, and accessibility in cultural heritage projects

7.4. A bilateral exchange between INCULTUM and the members of its Network

The contribution of INCULTUM to the Network is based on a bilateral relationship. On one hand, INCULTUM is sharing among the members of the Network, on the website and on the Zenodo INCULTUM Community, the results it has produced (e.g. those described in sections 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3 above). On the other hand, INCULTUM offers to the members of the Network the opportunity to share their results.

This is implemented through the section 'Resources from the Network' in the INCULTUM Training Portal. In this section, a list of links is provided to individual resources as well as open repositories provided by the members of the Network.

Resources from the Network

[\[2\] >> Resources from the network](#)

Targets: public administrators, tourism professionals, cultural managers

In this section you can find outcomes, guidance, recommendations and good practices in the fields of cultural promotion of territories, tourism related promotion of cultural heritage promotion and access to cultural heritage resources in the digital realm.

The following materials and links are collected from the stakeholders participating in the [INCULTUM Network](#).

The links to the materials is provided below, by the alphabetical order of the provider names.

Be.CULTOUR
Digital Culture Tourism

by Be.CULTOUR, H2020 project

Webinar series about innovative approaches in the cultural tourism sector

[Access here all the events in 2023 and 2024 \(link\)](#)

EUREKA3D

Webinar series about data, metadata and paradata in 3D digitisation of cultural heritage

Access here to the webinars run in collaboration with the UNESCO Chair on Digital Cultural Heritage run by Cyprus University of Technology (CUT) in partner of EUREKA3D and also TEXTOUR and IMPACTOUR projects. It has been the author of the VIGRE Study commissioned by EU on quality of 3D digitisation of tangible cultural heritage that has been at the basis of the two seminars.

[VIGRE Study 2023/2024 on quality in 3D digitisation of tangible cultural heritage >>>](#)

The seminars explored the status of 3D digitisation of cultural heritage in the world

[Webinars: Paradata, Metadata & Data in 2D/3D Digital Heritage Documentation >>>](#)

Type / to choose a block

européana

by Europeana Foundation, The Netherlands

- [Copyright Management Guidelines for Cultural Heritage Institutions \(PDF\)](#)
- [Guide and Q&A \(PDF\)](#) to accurately label digital cultural heritage
- [Visual step-by-step Flow Chart \(PDF\)](#) for rights labelling

EUROPEAN CULTURAL HERITAGE SKILLS ALLIANCE

by European Cultural Heritage Skills Alliance

Report and model describing current heritage professions

[A new landscape for heritage professions - preliminary findings](#)

IMPACTOUR

by IMPACTOUR, H2020 project

Report on cultural tourism leading to sustainable economic and social development

[Report on Cultural Tourism Leading to Sustainable Economic and Social Development \(PDF\)](#)

IN SITU

by IN SITU, Horizon Europe project

The report developed by the University of Utrecht and published by the IN SITU project in October 2023, challenges the conventional wisdom on diversification opportunities in non-urban regions.

[New domains in CCIs in non-urban regions \(PDF\)](#)

PHOTOCONSORTIUM

by Photoconsortium International Consortium for Photographic Heritage

Initiatives, tools and useful resources about access and educational reuse of digital cultural heritage contents available online

[Photoconsortium Educational Portal >>>](#)

Type / to choose a block

RURALIZATION

by RURALIZATION, H2020 project

MDOC: "Creating New Opportunities in Rural Areas", 1 March - 12 April 2023

[Event in EUX \(link\)](#)

ruAllure

by ruAllure, H2020 project

[Scientific publications >>>](#)

RURITAGE

by RURITAGE, H2020 project

Regeneration of rural areas through heritage-led plans

[RURITAGE Community-Based Methodology \(PDF\)](#)

SPOT

by SPOT, H2020 project

Outcomes of a multi-national study conducted in 15 countries about the development of cultural tourism in Europe

[SPOT Policy Briefs >>>](#)

TEXTOUR

by TEXTOUR, H2020 project

[TEXTOUR Resources >>>](#)

tourism 4.0
ENHANCED TOURISM EXPERIENCE

by tourism 4.0 project, edited by ARCTUR d.o.o., Slovenia

[Digital Innovation of Cultural Heritage \(PDF\)](#)

Handbook for tourist destinations and cultural heritage institutions

unesco
World Heritage Convention

World Heritage Cultural Landscapes
[A Handbook for Conservation and Management](#)

Figure 17 Resources from the Network linked from the INCULTUM Training Portal

These resources include different types of links, depending on the way that each networked project or organisation manages the access to its resources.

MOOC:

- Creating New Opportunities in Rural Areas, by Ruralisation, H2020 project

Documents downloadable in PDF format

- Regeneration of rural areas through heritage-led plans, by Ruritage, H2020 project
- Report on Cultural Tourism Leading to Sustainable Economic and Social Development by IMPACTOUR, H2020 project
- New domains in Cultural and Creative Industries in non-urban regions, by IN SITU, Horizon Europe project
- Handbook for tourist destinations and cultural heritage institutions edited by Tourism 4.0 initiative of Arctur S.o.o.
- World Heritage Cultural Landscapes - A Handbook for Conservation and Management, UNESCO World Heritage Convention
- A new landscape for heritage professions – preliminary findings, by the European Cultural Heritage Skills Alliance CHARTER
- Copyright Management Guidelines for Cultural Heritage Institutions, Guide to label digital cultural

heritage, Visual step-by-step Flow Chart for rights labelling edited by Europeana Foundation

- Study on quality in 3D digitisation of tangible cultural heritage by European Commission and promoted by Eureka3D, DEP project

Webinars

- Webinar series about innovative approaches in the cultural tourism sector organised by Be.CULTOUR, H2020 project
- Webinar series about paradata, metadata and data for 3D acquisition in cultural heritage by Eureka3D, DEP project

Links to repositories

- Educational portal, by Photoconsortium International Association, accredited aggregator of Data Space for Cultural Heritage
- RurAllure Scientific publications, H2020 project
- SPOT Reports and Outcomes, H2020 project
- TExTOUR Resources, H2020 project

8. Collaborations and participation in third party's events

The scope of task 6.3 has been to establish a community of organisations that were not part of the INCULTUM consortium, with the aim to create a network of collaborations in the light of future take-up of the project's strategies for tourist promotion of peripheral areas. This effort was shared with WP2 focusing on outreach activities with the aim to raise awareness of the project to the widest audience.

The work of Task 6.3 in the initial period was based on establishing contacts with various projects and organizations and all the partners participated in this effort by leveraging their own networks of colleagues and peers. A simple collaboration form was created to formalize the relationship between INCULTUM and the other stakeholders. The form has been used to establish the terms of the collaboration and to fulfil the requirements of GDPR, by asking to the other organisations and projects to confirm their agreement to be included in the list of collaborations published on the INCULTUM website and in the INCULTUM mailing list used for the distribution of the newsletter.

The local activities carried out in the pilots represented a great occasion for establishing new collaborations, too at local level.

The promotion was bidirectional. As illustrated in Chapter 5 the collaborations are enlisted in a dedicated page on the INCULTUM project's website and promoted via blogs and social media posting. In parallel, as illustrated in Chapter 6, INCULTUM has been promoted in the websites of the networked initiatives.

The contacts with the projects and organisations participating in the Network are included in the project's mailing list to receive the INCULTUM newsletter.

In addition to the cross-promotion, the collaborations developed in practical terms at three levels.

The first level of collaboration occurred in the frame of the networking events organised at Euromed 2022 Conference and at ESRA 2023 Congress. Further details about the networking events are provided in deliverable D2.3

The second level of collaboration consisted in the participation of INCULTUM representatives in the events organized by other members of the network. These are listed in the section 8.1 below.

The third level of collaboration refers to the activities carried out jointly with the sister projects. These are listed in the section 8.2 below.

8.1. Participation of INCULTUM in third-party events

A wide range of presentations have been delivered by the INCULTUM partners in several events organised by other projects and initiatives.

All these interventions have been promoted on the INCULTUM blog with dedicated news.

The presentations are gathered and accessible on the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

A selection of the international events where INCULTUM has been invited is reported here as a reference, to demonstrate the richness of the interventions carried during the whole project period.

- RE-CULTURAL HERITAGE Meeting: Empowering Heritage Communities, Thessaloniki, 11-12 March 2024
- Be.CULTOUR Webinar 5: Community-led and innovative entrepreneurship for circular cultural tourism, online, 23/6/2023
- VI Meeting of University Community Volunteers and Solidarity Associations, Granada, 12/4/2023
- Water Path: Heritage-based solutions and community-based cultural tourism, Faro, 14/4/2023
- Coffee with Letters, Faro, 24/3/2023
- Winter School: A New Grand Tour in Tuscany, Tourism between heritage, knowledge and digital media,

Lajatico and Lucca, February 2023

- Man and Biosphere conference, 15/2/2023
- 1st Polish Conference on Cultural Economics, 24/11/2022
- Cultures of Water: Heritage, Environment and Society, Porto, 18/11/2022
- Widen European Access to cultural communities Via Europeana final conference, 16/9/2022
- Horto Aquam Salutarem final conference, Lisbon, 26/9/2022
- The role of photographic heritage in empowering communities' participation in cultural heritage, Pisa, 28/6/2022
- RURITAGE Final Conference, Paris, 10/6/2022
- Excavated Habitat and Cultural Landscape: International Colloquium Culture of Deserts, Guadix, 23/3/2022
- INCULTUM presented as experience of participation at Information Day – Horizon Europe, Granada, 24/2/2022
- Winter school: Digital Cultural Tourism and Diplomacy, Limassol, 14/2/2022
- Smart Governance in local municipalities – Innovative approaches to city and municipality management, online, 23/11/2021
- Europeana 2021: Recover, Rebuild, Grow, online, 20/11/2021

8.2. Collaborations with sister projects

Six H2020 funded projects (IMPACTOUR, SPOT, SmartCulTour, TExTOUR, INCULTUM, Be.CULTOUR) convened in Lisbon on 5 July 2022 under the coordination of UNINOVA, to share research results and common experiences in the evaluation, management and development of Cultural Tourism across European regions with the objective to provide recommendations to the EU policy making authorities.

Then, two events focused on the connection between the sister projects funded in the ambit of the same call Transformations-04 of Horizon 2020:

- The Policy roundtable of EU-funded projects on sustainable cultural tourism
- The International Conference on Cultural Tourism

EU Policy Roundtable, 11 October 2022

The Policy roundtable of EU-funded projects on sustainable cultural tourism was held online on 11 October 2022 between European Policy Makers and representatives of the six projects funded in the Transformations-04 call dedicated to sustainable tourism.

Figure 18 News on the INCULTUM blog about the joint Policy Roundtable

The discussion was very fruitful and addressed several policy making issues, such as:

- EU Policy
- Europeanisation
- EC Research & Innovation coordination
- Innovation
- Europeanisation
- Sustainable Development
- Infrastructure
- Implementation
- Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation

This meeting happens as a consequence of the meeting held in Lisbon, at UNINOVA.

Report on policy recommendations by Horizon2020 Sustainable Cultural Tourism Projects

The outcomes of the meeting in Lisbon and of the online round table were summarized in a report that is available for download from the project’s website and its Policy Toolbox, as well as on the INCULTUM Zenodo Community. The main findings and outcomes illustrated in the report regard three main areas: (i) EU Policy and Europeanization, (ii) Research and Innovation, and (iii) Sustainability and Infrastructure.

Excerpt from the report:

“The main aim of the report has been to identify areas where additional policy attention can further strengthen the position of cultural tourism, support innovations and digital transitions, and protect sustainable development initiatives.”

The model for the development of sustainable cultural tourism development is illustrated in the report with the figure below.

Figure 19 Model for sustainable cultural tourism development (Extract from the joint recommendations report)

The network of collaborations established by INCULTUM belong to the three areas indicated in the report, namely: innovation, participation, and digitization.

Joint International Conference, 27-28 June 2023

The International Conference on Cultural Tourism held on 27-28 June 2023 was co-organized by Be.CULTOUR, IMPACTOUR, INCULTUM, SmartCulTour, SPOT and TEXTOUR, the EU H2020 projects operating the area of sustainable tourism promotion on the territory.

An overview of the outcomes of the six organizing projects was given, while good practices based on the finalized and ongoing experimentations in diverse European regions were identified and debated.

International Conference on Cultural Tourism Advances – Programme
27-28th June 2023

10:00	<p>Session 1: Lessons learnt from six Horizon 2020 projects in the field of cultural tourism</p> <p>General overview of the outcomes of the six organizing Horizon 2020 projects, identifying good practices based on the finalized and ongoing experimentations in diverse European regions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Milada Štastná (SPOT) ▪ João Martins (IMPACTOUR) ▪ Antonia Gravagnuolo (Be.CULTOUR) ▪ Daniel Basulto (TeXTOUR) ▪ Jose Maria Martin Civantos (INCULTUM) ▪ Bart Neuts (SmartCulTour)
10:30	Coffee break with demos of project results

Figure 20 International Conference on Cultural Tourism Advances

9. Key performance indicator

One KPI was provided in the Grant Agreement to monitor the achievement of the work in the ambit of INCULTUM Network.

From the Grant Agreement		From the project's execution
Unit of measure from the Grant Agreement	Target value	Achieved results
No. of collaboration agreements for the participation in the INCULTUM network	35-50	37 collaborations, as listed on the website In addition, all the pilots established a wide range of collaboration agreements with local public administrations.

The target value has been reached, as demonstrated through the previous chapters.

The work conducted by the pilots in their respective territories complements what is reported in this deliverable. Further details are provided in the pilots' report.

10. Conclusions

The dialogue and the collaborations established and illustrated in this deliverable allowed to run a critical review of the strategies and the models developed in the project by the INCULTUM Consortium, within a wider network of actors who share with INCULTUM a common interest in the exploitation of the role that cultural tourism can play for social, economic, and territorial cohesion.

The definition of protocols of collaboration with other projects, initiatives, and organizations at the beginning of the project facilitated the initial creation of the INCULTUM Network, conceived as an instrument of long-lasting relationships.

The network of common interest among these actors has engaged all in a programme of collaborations along the whole project's lifetime, culminated in the participation of some of the members of the INCULTUM Network in the project's final conference in Guadix on 23/4/2024.

The innovations proposed, developed and tested in INCULTUM and in its pilots - with particular regard to the construction and promotion of heritage communities, and the implementation of social service contracts - have been used, in a shared effort by the participants in the network, as benchmarks for the identification of good practices, lessons learnt, obstacles and threats, which were in turn reversed from the network back into the project and its pilots.

This happened via a continuous exchange of information, through the website, the blog, and the training portal.

The cooperation with the sister projects in Horizon 2020 brought to joint policy recommendations, demonstrating the added value of working together to contribute to the understanding of the impact of tourism on communities, local economy, and culture.

New directions of sustainable cultural tourism in the European peripheries have been considered. This was the case for example of the emergence of new cultural tourism products that are using advanced digital technologies and 3D digitalization, which has been possible to be observed via the collaboration with the digital initiatives participating the Network (e.g. those supported under the Digital Europe Programme of the EU).

The effort spent by all the partners towards the participation in the events organised by the other members of the network has been effective, strengthening liaisons that will continue to support future actions, both at pilot levels and internationally.